

IMPACT

ABSORBED ENERGY, DAMAGE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT OF GLASS
FIBRE EPOXY COMPOSITES

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AIM

The final aim of this study on impact damage of composites is to understand the relation between three characteristic data: the impact energy, the impact damage and the residual mechanical properties of the impacted composite. This paper will briefly describe the experimental approach, and further enlighten the important role of some test parameters. Finally, it will be shown how the use of image processing techniques for ultrasonic C-scan can help in understanding the relation between damage and residual mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

An instrumented falling weight impact tester (IFWIT) has been designed and constructed. With falling weight masses ranging from 0.5 to 2.5 kg and heights from 0.5 to 2m, the impact energy ranges from 2 to 50J. A flexible specimen gripping system enables us to verify the influence of different gripping conditions: the opening can have a diameter of 40 or 80 mm, the gripping force can be adjusted by controlling the torque moment on four screws.

Impact force and impact velocity (at 5mm before impact) are measured, digitised and stored. Postprocessing of data results in five plots

(force, energy, velocity and deflection versus time and force versus deflection) and a set of numerical results (see fig. 1).

INFLUENCE OF TEST PARAMETERS

Any detailed literature review will show that test conditions, used by different authors, can vary considerably. The influence of different mass-velocity combinations to obtain the same impact energy has been discussed by several authors. However, almost no attention has been paid on the influence of specimen dimensions and gripping conditions. In this study, the composite plate is gripped between two steel plates with circular openings. Two different diameters have been considered: 40 and 80 mm. Two clamping forces are applied: the former allows free slipping between the steel plates ("loose"), the latter prevents any slipping ("fixed"). So, four different test conditions have been evaluated.

All tests have been carried out on a glass epoxy crossply laminate (SCOTCHPLY 1002) with stacking sequence $[0,90,0,90,0]_s$, ply thickness 0.254 mm and total thickness of 2.29 mm. The impact specimen dimensions are 100 x 100 mm. Some results just confirm the theoretical predictions: the maximum force during impact increases with decreasing grip opening, whereas the maximum deflection decreases. The influence of the clamping force is negligible.

On the other hand, the absorbed energy is very much influenced by the grip opening (fig. 2): for the same total impact energy, the absorbed energy increases by a factor 2, when changing from 80 to 40 mm opening diameter. This can be rationalised as follows: the total impact energy is, during the impact, used for elastic deformation of the composite plate (E_{e1}) and is partially absorbed by the composite plate (E_{abs}); as will be explained later, the latter part is the sum of damping energy loss (E_{vibr}) and of the energy used to create damage in the composite (E_{dam}). Simple calculations show that for the same total energy the elastic part has to be larger when the grip opening is larger, hence leaving a smaller part of the total energy available for damping and damage.

RESIDUAL STRENGTH MEASUREMENTS

Both residual tensile and compression strength have been measured. Specimen width is 25 and 50 mm for tensile and 25 mm for compression specimens; specimen total length is 100 mm, free length (in between the grips) is 40mm for tensile and 20mm for compression specimens (ITTRI-type).

From the experimental data, several conclusions can be drawn:

a. the ratio R of residual tensile strength to the original tensile strength drops to a value of 0.5 at $E_{abs} = 10$ J (fig 3a). Although the spread on the results is important, a small influence of gripping force and a large influence of grip opening has been identified (fig 3b), even when the residual strength is plotted versus the **absorbed** energy; when plotted versus the **total** energy, the influence is even greater.

This means that **neither total nor absorbed energy can be used as a unique parameter, which is independent of the test method and the test apparatus.** This explains further why experimental results of different authors on similar materials can be so incoherent. The reason is that part of the absorbed energy is dissipated in vibration and damping (E_{vibr}), which depends on the specimen geometry and the gripping conditions. Hence, the remaining part (E_{dam}) will vary, and so the damage in the specimen (as will be shown later). As only the damage affects the residual properties, a correlation

$$R = f(E_{dam}) \quad (1)$$

should be unique, but not the relation

$$\begin{aligned} R &= f(E_{abs}) \\ &= f(E_{vibr} + E_{dam}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

- b. similar tendencies as in a. have been found for residual stiffness and strain to failure.
- c. in the impact energy range, considered in this study, the width of the tensile test specimen has a marginal influence.

- d. compressive residual strength data show even a faster drop as absorbed energy increases : $R = 0.5$ is reached already at $E_{abs} = 5$ J (fig 5). Detailed investigation of the damage will explain this effect.

Study of IMPACT DAMAGE using ULTRASONIC C-SCAN and LIGHT MICROSCOPY

The impact damage has been monitored in two ways :

- first, optical microscopy on polished sections through the impact point in 0° and 90° direction, reveal the individual delaminations and matrix cracks, spreading out towards the bottom side of the composite plate (fig 5).
- second, ultrasonic C-scan has been used to quantify the damage zone area. Plotting the damage zone area versus the absorbed energy (fig 6) a non-linear relation is found, which confirms the earlier statement that the energy, dissipated in damage, is a variable part of the absorbed energy.

Moreover, the difference in absorbed energy for the same total impact energy but different gripping conditions, as shown in fig 2, results similarly in a non-unique relation between damage zone area and total impact energy (fig 7). This non-uniqueness remains if we plot the damage zone area versus the absorbed energy (fig 8). This again is a confirmation of an earlier statement, expressed in formula (2) : as we do not know the part of the absorbed energy which is used for the creation of damage, the relation between the absorbed energy and the damage zone area cannot be a unique one.

Finally, one more complication has to be added : comparing fig 3b and fig 8, one can observe that, although the specimens tested with the layer grip opening ($\varnothing 80$ mm) show a larger damage zone (fig 8), their tensile strength is less affected than in the case of the 40 mm grip opening diameter. This observation strongly suggests that different damage modes can be present in damage zones of the same size, and that these damage modes depend on the gripping conditions. Hence, there is a need for refinement of the ultrasonic-C-scan, in order to be able to discriminate between different damage modes.

For this reason, the ultrasonic C-scan has further been developed to allow image processing of the digitised 3D-image, namely of the amplitude of the reflected US-beam as a function of the planar coordinates of the composite plate. Variable threshold black/white images and contour line plots reveal additional information, a.o. a central damage-free zone at low impact energies, and a diffuse, widespread damage over the whole plate at high impact energies. Further statistical analysis will enable us to correlate in a quantitative and rational way the impact damage and the residual strength after impact.

CONCLUSIONS

1. This mainly experimental study clearly shows the importance of test parameters on the damage created during and the residual strength after impact. The diameter of the circular opening of the gripping device has been identified as the most influential test parameter.
2. Attempts to set up a unique relation between absorbed energy and residual strength failed. This has been rationalised by the statement that the absorbed energy itself is the sum of vibrational and damage energy.
3. Damage zone area, using ultrasonic C-scan, increases with absorbed energy, but the relation is neither linear nor unique. Moreover, different damage modes have been observed. Hence, a study to refine the C-scan technique using image processing techniques, has been started.

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Fig. 1: Presentation of postprocessed data of an impact test.

Fig. 2: Influence of impact test parameters on absorbed energy

Fig. 3: Residual tensile strength versus absorbed energy for glass epoxy crossply.

Fig. 4: Residual compressive strength versus absorbed energy for glass-epoxy crossply (as in fig. 3a)

Fig 5 : matrix cracks and delaminations as revealed by optical microscopy on polished cross-sections (scetch)

Fig. 6: damage zone area versus absorbed energy for glass-epoxy crossply

Fig. 7: Damage area versus total impact energy

Fig. 8: Damage area versus absorbed impact energy